

Properties of Pure Sodium Soaps of Saturated Fatty Acids

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Pure sodium salts of odd and even chain fatty acids (C_7^o to C_{19}^o) were prepared and their properties and performance characteristics were evaluated.

The odd and even chain fatty acid soaps, in water, appear to behave as two separate surfactant series with respect to their solubility and critical micelle concentration; the higher soaps behave somewhat anomalously perhaps due to coiling of longer hydrophobic chains in aqueous solutions, while the lower soaps having very high CMC are ineffective as surfactants at the usual concentrations.

MANY reports have appeared on the properties of sodium soaps of fatty acids having even number of C-atoms originating from natural fatty oils¹. Reports on some properties of odd chain fatty acid soaps have started appearing only recently^{2,3}. Due to differences in test conditions of different workers, it is not possible to compare the properties of odd and even chain fatty acid salts at any given temperature. A detailed comparative study of the properties of sodium salts of fatty acids, from heptanoic to nonadecanoic, was, therefore, taken up.

Experimental

Preparation of sodium salts of pure fatty acids: Four odd chain saturated fatty acids, viz. tri-, penta-, hepta- and nonadecanoic acids, were synthesized by the nitrile route⁴. GLC-pure methyl esters of even chain fatty acids were reduced to fatty alcohols by the sodium reduction method, which were then converted to iodides from which nitriles were prepared. The nitriles were hydrolysed by alcoholic NaOH and the soaps obtained were freed from unreacted impurities by repeated crystallizations from alcohol. All the other pure acids were prepared from the commercial fatty acids by the usual ester fractionation technique and, wherever necessary, by hydrogenation and/or solvent crystallization. The melting points of the glc and tlc pure fatty acids (purity of over 99.9%) agree closely with earlier reported values^{5,6,7}. The relationship of m.p. with the number of C-atoms in the acids is shown in Fig. 1a. The pure fatty acids taken in alcohol were neutralised with alcoholic sodium hydroxide and the soaps were purified by recrystallization from alcohol, dried and stored in a desiccator.

Evaluation of the properties and performance characteristics of soaps in water: The pure soaps were evaluated by the methods described earlier⁸⁻¹⁰.

The temperature at which 1% aqueous soap solution becomes clear (K. P.) and the temperature at which clouding occurs while gradually cooling the clear solutions (C. P.) are given in Table 1 and represented in Fig. 1 (b and c). pH of 0.25% aqueous solutions, interfacial tension (I. T.) of 0.1% solutions against

Fig. 1. Relationship of No. of C-atoms with (a) m.p. of fatty acids, (b) K.P. of fatty acid soaps and (c) C. P. of fatty acid soaps.

toluene and the minimum surface tension values (S. T.) attained by the soap solutions are given in Table 1. Critical micelle concentrations (CMC) of the soaps obtained by graphical methods from the S. T. and conductivity data of solutions varying in concentration are also given in Table 1. The relationship of log molar CMC (by conductivity method) and the number of C-atoms in soap is

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shown in Fig. 2. All the properties and performance characteristics of the soaps were evaluated, at 60°, in distilled water except the S. T. determinations which were in presence of added sodium meta silicate (5% based on soap).

Fig. 2. Relationship of log molar CMC of sodium salts and No. of C-atoms present.

of one C-atom to an even chain fatty acid soap (upto palmitate) means effective increase in the chain length by about 1.5 C-atoms from the solubility considerations, while for the odd chain soaps it means reducing effective chain length by less than one C-atom (about 0.5).

The pH of 0.25% solutions of different soaps progressively increases with increasing chain length (7.2 to 10.3 for decanoate to nonadecanoate) indicating the tendency of higher soaps for greater hydrolysis in distilled water. The same trend is observed (results not given) at different concentrations studied and also at 30°. The calculated maximum percentage hydrolysis for C_7 and C_{19} soaps, at 60°, are 115.2×10^{-4} and 27.4×10^{-4} , respectively, and the other soaps have values in-between, but the concentrations at which maximum percentage hydrolysis occurs differ for different soaps.

Sodium myristate is the best amongst the soaps in respect of I. T. lowering power. The ability, however, decreases when the series is either ascended or descended indicating the need for a proper HLB.

The need for optimum HLB is also apparent in the various performance characteristics of the soaps studied at 60° (but not reported in the table). In the wetting tests (canvas disc method¹⁰ using 0.1% soap solutions) sodium laurate was found to be the best (wetting time of 31 sec) followed by hendecanoate (38 sec) and tridecanoate (60 sec),

TABLE 1—PROPERTIES OF AQUEOUS SOAP SOLUTIONS AT 60°

No. of Carbon atoms in soap	K. P. °C	C. P. °C	pH of 0.25% solution	I. T. of 0.1% soln. (dynes/cm)	Min. S. T. (dynes/cm)	CMC, m moles/l	
						S. T. method	Conductivity method
7	*	*	—	32	40	461	467
8	*	*	—	33	39	301	301
9	*	*	—	32	36	139	136
10	*	*	7.2	31	34	103	106
11	24.3	10.7	7.6	29	34	40	38
12	28.1	16.0	7.6	28	31	30	31
13	41.2	31.4	8.6	26	28	13	12
14	43.9	35.3	9.1	20	27	8	9
15	57.4	50.0	9.4	27	24	3.6	3.8
16	61.3	54.3	9.8	30	22	2.7	2.9
17	73.2	66.8	10.0	31	26	1.7	1.7
18	75.5	68.0	10.2	33	27	0.8	0.9
19	83.6	77.2	10.3	34	36	0.9	0.9

* Clear at 0°

Results and Discussion

The solubility of the soaps progressively decreases with the increase in their molecular weight as shown by the progressive changes of K. P. and C. P. (Table 1). However, when K. P. (Fig. 1b) and C. P. (Fig. 1c) are plotted against the number of C-atoms present in the soap, the points for odd and even chain acid soaps fall on two separate lines, as for the m.p. of fatty acids (Fig. 1a). The K. P. and C. P. lines of odd chain fatty acid salts are above those of the even chain, whereas the m.p. line of the odd chain fatty acids is below that of the even chain acids. The figure indicates that the addition

while the rest of the soaps are poor wetting agents under the test conditions. The 0.25% solutions of salts from heptanoate to decanoate do not foam in the Ross-Miles pour foam test¹¹ at 60° and hendecanoate gives poor unstable foam (only 55 mm). The other soaps, laurate to palmitate in distilled water, foam better than sodium lauryl alcohol sulphate (NaLAS) but again foaming ability decreases as the molecular weight increases. However, as adjudged by the foam height after 5 min, the stability of foam formed increases as the molecular weight increases. The deterative power (in the soiled cotton fabric-washing tests using Tergo-o-Meter⁹)

of higher soaps (tetradecanoate and above) is better than NaLAS, while the lower ones are poorer. The detergency of 0.25% soap solutions from heptanoate to hendecanoate are only 10-12% of that of sodium stearate. In general, the medium chain fatty acid soaps showed poor performance characteristics and are ineffective as surfactants at the tested concentrations (normally employed).

In all cases, the S. T. decreases with increase in the concentration till around the CMC of the soap, and the minimum values obtained are given in Table 1. The S. T. lowering power (effectiveness) is maximum for palmitate and pentadecanoate, amongst the soaps of even and odd series, respectively. The effectiveness decreases if the chain length is either increased or decreased, showing the need for optimum HLB for effective S. T. reduction.

CMC values of the soaps in distilled water obtained by the conductivity method are close to those obtained by the S. T. method (Table 1). They are also nearer to the values obtained by the pinacyanol chloride dye method (not reported).

The short chain fatty acid soaps (caprate and below) will be effective only at a very high concentration (as CMC of caprate is 2% by weight) which is not encountered in actual usage. The CMC, in general, decreases with increase in the chain length till stearate and there is no perceptible effect by further increase in the chain length by one more $-\text{CH}_2$ group. When log molar CMC is plotted against the number of C-atoms in the soap molecules, a very interesting picture emerges (Fig. 2). Two separate straight lines are obtained for odd and even chain acid soaps upto palmitate, indicating that the odd and even chain soaps behave as two separate surfactant series. It is apparent from Fig. 2 that increasing the acyl chain of odd chain fatty acid

soap by one CH_2 group (next higher even chain fatty acid soap) appears to increasing the effective chain length (ECL) by only 0.6 CH_2 group till palmitate. Conversely, increase in one CH_2 group in even chain fatty acid soap means increase in ECL by 1.4 CH_2 group. The anomalous solubility behaviour and CMC data may be due to the difference in intermolecular attraction forces between the acyl chains having odd and even number of C-atoms and/or due to the difference in arrangement of soap molecules in micelles. The CMC of the heptadecanoate falls on the line of even chain fatty acid soaps while nonadecanoate has CMC which is the same as that of the stearate. This behaviour of the higher soaps in water may be due to the coiling tendency of their long hydrophobic acyl chains as postulated by Mukerjee^{1,2}.

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